

Structural and energetic properties of P3HT and PCBM layers on the Ag(111) surface

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Abstract

The structural and energetic properties of poly(3-hexyl-thiophene) (P3HT) and 6,6-phenyl C61 butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM) monolayers and multilayers on the Ag(111) surface are investigated using classical force fields and molecular dynamics simulations. The results demonstrate that P3HT has a stronger interaction with the substrate, while PCBM exhibits larger monolayer formation energy due to stronger intermolecular interactions. In addition, PCBM prefers a “tail-up” conformation by orienting the phenyl and butyric acid methyl ester groups away from the surface, thus favoring a denser packing, while relaxation of intermolecular order in P3HT is found to initiate above 450 K. For the simulations a new parameterization of the General Amber Force Field involving dihedral angles and interactions with the Ag(111) substrate was developed. The new parameters were validated successfully against available crystal structures and ab initio data.

Keywords: Organic Photovoltaics, P3HT, PCBM, Silver, Force Field, Adsorption, Molecular Dynamics

1. Introduction

Hybrid heterostructures involving organic material thin films on inorganic substrates demonstrate unique properties which are radically different from their isolated components [1,2]. For appropriately chosen materials, the interfacial electrical, magnetic and optical properties can be engineered to realize new device functionalities, with many applications in organic electronics including light-emitting diodes, field-effect transistors, and solar cells [3-6]. Charge injection, trapping and recombination also strongly depend on the interface molecular arrangement. Understanding and tailoring the interface microstructure is thus of great technological interest.

Adsorption and arrangement of organic species on the substrate are mainly controlled by the generally weak substrate-organic interactions while intermolecular interactions between the organic molecules affect the organization within the adsorbate film [7]. Strong intermolecular interactions in some molecules may nevertheless also influence the supramolecular assembly [8,9]. It is the interplay between these two factors that finally determines the microstructure at the interface.

Poly-3-hexyl-thiophene (P3HT) is a thiophene based conjugated polymer used as an electron donor material in organic solar cells. Bulk heterojunction (BHJ) devices may be fabricated by mixing P3HT with 6,6-phenyl C61 butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM) which is used as an electron acceptor [10]. Although nowadays a vast selection of other material options have been investigated, P3HT:PCBM remains a prototypical system of reference and thus a useful material for studying organic/substrate interfaces. Of interest is the case of a metallic substrate, either in the form of a metal contact or in the form of a plasmonic metal nanoparticle embedded inside the BHJ [11].

The interaction with a silver substrate has been investigated both experimentally and computationally. On the experimental side, oligothiophenes are found to lie flat on the Ag(111) surface [12-20], while the difficulty in obtaining ordered films and controlling their properties has been discussed in the literature extensively [21-23]. Oligothiophenes on the Ag(111) surface have also been studied computationally, mostly by *ab initio* methods, which have mainly determined their adsorption sites and classified their corresponding interactions [24-27]. On the other hand, classical molecular dynamics, offer the opportunity to explore the supramolecular structures formed on the surface. For example,

sexithiophenes were found to form highly ordered strips with the all-trans conformation situated parallel to the substrate, while most of the sulfur atoms reside 3.2 Å above the bridge sites [25]. In addition, by comparing quaterthiophene and sexithiophene deposited along with C60 it was observed that longer chains exhibit greater order, however when C60 was deposited first, the oligomers were aligned along the corrugations between C60 molecules [26].

In this work the energetics of P3HT and PCBM adsorption on the Ag(111) surface are investigated and compared using classical force field calculations. Dependence on coverage and temperature is also examined. In order to achieve an accurate description, a reparameterization of the General Amber Force Field was performed where the inter-ring and side chain torsional potentials were adjusted according to ab initio calculations. Polarization of the metallic surface was taken into account using the image charge method.

2. Computational methods

2.1 Force field construction

A crucial part of molecular dynamics simulations of hybrid systems is the force field used to describe the intermolecular and metal-organic interactions. Concerning the intermolecular interactions, it is established by now that general purpose force fields are not able to correctly describe the inter-ring torsional potential in conjugated thiophene systems and hence a reparameterization is necessary. The torsional potential of 2,2'-bithiophene, has been investigated by Raos et al. [28] using high accuracy first principles methods. Marcon and Raos [29] developed an improved force field for thiophene derivatives while Widge et al. [30] reported parameters consistent with the General Amber Force Field for poly(alkyl-thiophenes), using however the torsional potential of bithiophene. Moreno et al. [31] parameterized the OPLS-AA force field and successfully replicated the crystal structures of α -quaterthiophene, α -sexithiophene and other alkyl-substituted oligomers. Pizzirusso et al. [32] parameterized the AMBER force field for sexithiophene and the new parameters were validated against two polymorph structures of sexithiophene reproducing a phase transition at about 580 K. To and Adams developed an accurate force field for P3HT [33] improving upon the works of Cheung et al. [34] and Marcon and Raos [29] by adjusting the torsional contributions. Ab initio studies on oligomers of 3-hexylthiophene reported that the barrier of the torsional potential depends on oligomer length

and converges at around 8 monomers [35, 36]. Based on this finding and by adjusting the torsional terms of the side chains, an improved force field was developed for P3HT by Bhatta et al. [37].

Metal-molecule interactions require however a different treatment since the electronic polarization induced on the surface by the organic material may play an important role. Iori et al. developed the GolP force field [38], as an extension of OPLS-AA by introducing a new type of atom on the metal surface in order to accurately reproduce adsorption sites. Polarization effects were also accounted for by introducing a method that mimics the effect of image charges [39]. This approach has been successfully implemented for different metal surfaces such as Au(100), Ag(111) and Ag(100) using CHARMM and AMBER to study the adsorption of proteins and nucleobases [40-43]. Nevertheless, simpler approaches can also be found in the literature. For example Heinz et al. [44] developed Lennard-Jones parameters intended to be used with a wide range of force fields to describe the interaction of organic materials with a metallic surface.

In this work an octamer of 3-hexyl-thiophene (3HT8) is used as a model for P3HT while a thiophene octamer (T8) is used for the parameterization of the backbone dihedral angle. Schematics of the main structural units for T8 and 3HT8 are depicted in Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b respectively. The inter-ring dihedral angle α is defined by atoms ss-cd-cd-ss for both molecules while dihedral angle β is defined by atoms c3-c3-cc-cd at the bond that connects the ring with the hexyl- side chain.

For the rotational profiles, standard density functional theory (DFT) was employed using B3LYP [45] as the exchange and correlation functional along with the 6-31G+(d,p) basis set. This selection was based on previous results [28,36] demonstrating that B3LYP/6-31G+(d,p) is accurate for modeling conjugated oligothiophene systems. In this framework, two types of computations were performed. Initially a full structure optimization was executed. The vibrational frequencies of the lowest energy structures were examined in order to confirm that the stationary points found by the optimizer were true minima. Then a series of single point computations were used to extract the torsional potentials around the bonds of interest.

For all force field simulations the General Amber Force Field (GAFF) [46] was used. A general purpose widely available force field was chosen because of its ability to describe several molecular species in a simulation, even though force fields specifically for

oligothiophenes and oligo-3hexyl-thiophenes are available in the literature [33,37]. The default torsional parameters in GAFF do not correctly describe the corresponding potential energy curves and in addition, parameters for the interaction of organic species with the metallic substrate are lacking. Therefore two different types of parameterization on the GAFF force field had to be pursued and developed: a) a new set of torsional parameters and b) parameters for the interaction of organic molecules with the Ag(111) substrate.

2.2 Molecular dynamics simulations

In order to construct realistic 3HT8 or PCBM configurations on top of the Ag(111) surface a procedure resembling vapor phase deposition was performed. Initially an Ag(111) surface with dimensions 102x100 Å was prepared and equilibrated for 50ps at 1000 K. At each deposition step a single 3HT8 or PCBM molecule with random initial position and velocity was inserted in the simulation box above the Ag surface. An NVE simulation was then executed for 35 ps to allow the molecule to reach the surface. Once the molecule landed on the surface an additional NVT simulation was performed for 30ps to equilibrate the system. The procedure was repeated until a full monolayer was delivered. During the simulation, if a molecule escaped the surface it was removed before initiating the next deposition step.

Interaction energies of the adsorbates were calculated in all cases by applying the following relaxation protocol: Initially the sample was heated and equilibrated at the desired initial temperature for 40 ps in the NVT ensemble. Then it was slowly cooled down to 0K over the course of 15 ps in case of a single molecule or 1 ns in case of deposited monolayers. To get a reliable estimate for the electrostatic interactions between the adsorbates and the surface, an averaging for 300 ps was performed with molecules fixed at their equilibrium positions.

All ab initio computations were performed with the Gaussian03 [47] package while force field simulations were performed using the NAMD [48] and LAMMPS [49] packages. Pre and post-processing as well as the calculation of partial atomic charges were handled by AmberTools [50] and our own in-house code. For the least squares fitting of the force field parameters the Merlin optimization environment [51] was used. A time step of 1 fs and a cutoff of 10Å were used in all molecular dynamics simulations.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Potential energy models

In order to develop the torsional parameters for angles α and β , one first needs to obtain the partial atomic charges. For all molecules used in this study, partial atomic charges were determined by a fit on the electrostatic potential using the standard RESP procedure [52]. Initially the structure was optimized at the B3LYP/6-31G+(d,p) level and then the electrostatic potential was obtained by a single point computation at the HF/6-31G* level. This choice was dictated by the requirement that our parameters be compatible with the rest of the GAFF force field. Partial charges for all molecules used in this work are provided in the supplementary material.

For the parameterization of dihedral α , the simpler T8 molecule was used as a model system. Fig. 2a shows the corresponding calculated ab initio torsional profile. There are two local minima at 15° and 180° , with the latter being energetically preferred. This is in agreement with the work of Bhatta et al [36] and Darling and Stenberg [35] who determined the positions of the minima at 20° , 180° and 15° , 180° respectively. The relative energy difference between the two minima was found to be 1.04 kcal/mol, compared to 1.05 kcal/mol [36] and 0.78 kcal/mol [35], while the barrier for a transition from 180° to 15° was found to be 4.57 kcal/mol, slightly overestimated compared to 3.74 kcal/mol [36] and 3.60 kcal/mol [35].

In order to properly incorporate the new ab initio torsional profile in the force field it is necessary to evaluate and subtract the contribution E_0 in the total energy coming from the rest of the energy terms (bond stretching, angle bending, VdW and electrostatic interactions, and contributions from all other dihedral angles). Hence the total potential energy is written as $E_{tot} = E_0 + E_\alpha$, where E_α is the torsional profile of interest in the force field. The contribution E_0 was obtained by an inversion method [32,53]. A molecular dynamics run was performed with a single T8 molecule in the canonical ensemble at 600K where the torsional potential for dihedral α was set to zero. After equilibration for 1 ns, the trajectory was sampled every 1 ps for 9 ns and the dihedral angle distribution $P_\alpha(\varphi)$ was obtained. Only the dihedral at the center of the 3HT8 backbone was used for the evaluation of $P_\alpha(\varphi)$ although in subsequent simulations all inter-ring dihedral angles were considered to be equivalent regardless of their position in the molecule. E_0 was then evaluated by the inversion scheme $E_0 = -k_B T \ln P_\alpha(\varphi)$. After subtracting from the ab initio profile, the

resulting torsional potential $E_\alpha = E_{tot} - E_0$ was fitted to a truncated Fourier series of the form

$$E_\alpha(\varphi) = \sum_n \frac{V_n}{2} (1 + \cos(n\varphi))$$

Four terms were deemed necessary to attain a good fit. Although more terms in the Fourier series improved the quality of the fit, the improvement was not enough to justify the additional computational cost in a simulation. The resulting parameters V_n are listed in Table 1, while the fitted profile is shown in Fig. 2a.

As a validation of the new torsional potential for dihedral α the crystal structure of T8 was used that has been experimentally identified by X-ray analysis [54]. It belongs to space group $P2_1/a$ with four T8 molecules in a monoclinic unit cell. Each T8 molecule was found to be in a perfectly planar arrangement. Using a molecular dynamics run in the isothermal-isobaric ensemble at 300 K, the cell dimensions a , b , c , the tilt angle β , and the density were calculated. The results are summarized in Table 2 along with the experimental values. All three cell dimensions differ from the experimental values by less than 0.14 Å while angle β of the monoclinic box was found to be 90.3° in good agreement with the experimental value of 90.31°. Similarly, the computed density 1.6 g/cm³ compares well with experimental value of 1.58 g/cm³ indicating that the force field with the new torsional potential reproduces successfully the known crystal structure of T8.

After obtaining the inter-ring torsional potential, dihedral β in 3HT8 was parameterized. The calculated ab initio torsional profile for dihedral β is shown in Fig. 2b. The profile has been obtained by rotation around the cc-c3 bond, while all other dihedrals in the hexyl- chain were set at the trans conformation and the inter-ring dihedrals α at 180°. The profile has two local minima at 85° and 180°, with the latter being energetically preferred. Their relative energy difference is 0.27 Kcal/mol while the barrier for a transition from 180° to 85° is 2.24 Kcal/mol. These values compare well with the DFT calculations by Bhatta et al [36] where the two minima were reported at 85° and 180°, while the relative energy difference and barrier were found to be 0.28 Kcal/mol and 1.97 Kcal/mol respectively.

The torsional angle distribution $P_\beta(\varphi)$ was obtained using the same procedure as for angle α . Only one hexyl- chain at the center of the molecule was used for the evaluation of

$P_\beta(\varphi)$ although in subsequent simulations all hexyl- chains were considered to be equivalent. After subtracting the contribution E_0 from the ab initio torsional profile, the result was fitted to a truncated Fourier series with four terms. The final force field parameters are listed in Table 1 while the fitted profile is shown in Fig. 2b.

In the development of force field parameters for the interaction with the Ag(111) surface the approach of Iori et al [38] and Hughes et al [43] was adopted. For the sake of completeness a brief description of the model is provided. The main idea is to account for the electronic polarization of the metal surface by attaching one end of a rigid rod at the position of each metal atom in the surface. The rod has a length of 0.7 Å, carries two opposite charges at its endpoints and is allowed to rotate freely. In practice a negative charge of 0.308e is assigned to silver atoms in the surface while a pseudo atom with mass 0.5 amu carries the opposite charge. Silver atoms in the surface layer (Ag_{SR}) are considered different from the ones in the lower layers (Ag_{LL}) and in addition virtual atoms (Ag_{SV}) are added in the surface layer so that adsorbed molecules adopt the correct binding positions. For each Ag_{SR} atom two virtual atoms are added at positions $(a/\sqrt{2}, a\sqrt{3}/2)$ and $(-a/\sqrt{2}, -a\sqrt{3}/2)$ with $a = 4.165$ Å being the lattice constant of Ag. Hence, an Ag(111) slab consists of three types of atoms Ag_{SR} , Ag_{LL} and Ag_{SV} ; all of them are held fixed during a simulation. The three different types of atoms used for silver are depicted in Fig. 3a, the positions of Ag_{SV} relative to Ag_{SR} are shown in Fig. 3b while a representation of the rod is given in Fig. 3c.

Organic molecules interact with the Ag surface through electrostatic interactions with the charged dipoles and through weak VdW interactions with the Ag_{SV} and Ag_{LL} atoms. For the latter a simple Lennard-Jones potential is used, having the form

$$V(r) = \varepsilon \left[\left(\frac{r_0}{r} \right)^{12} - 2 \left(\frac{r_0}{r} \right)^6 \right]$$

where ε is the well depth and r_0 the equilibrium separation. Six atom types were considered, namely Csp², S, O (carbonyl), O (hydroxyl), H (polar) and a general type (X) for all other atoms. For interactions involving Ag_{SR} atoms and organic species ε is set to zero, while Csp² atoms are allowed to interact only with Ag_{SV} atoms. Since atoms in the silver slab are not allowed to move, LJ interactions between all three Ag atom types are set to zero.

The twelve unknown parameters were determined using a least squares fit to adsorption energies and distances from the surface, for a series of simple molecules,

calculated using DFT and taken from [43]. The data were partitioned into two different sets: a) the fitting set, which consisted of 9 molecules, was used to adjust the force field parameters, and b) the validation set, which also consisted of 9 molecules, was used to validate the resulting parameters. The least squares fitting simultaneously adjusted all 12 parameters by minimizing the RMS error

$$RMS = \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{\text{fitting set}} \left(\frac{E_{ads}^{ref} - E_{ads}}{E_{ads}^{ref}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{d_{ads}^{ref} - d_{ads}}{d_{ads}^{ref}} \right)^2 \right]^{1/2}$$

where $E_{ads}^{ref}, d_{ads}^{ref}$ are the reference values for the adsorption energy and equilibrium distance from the Ag(111) surface, while E_{ads}, d_{ads} are the corresponding values calculated using the force field. E_{ads} and d_{ads} were obtained by applying the relaxation protocol described in section 2. The adsorption energy is then calculated as

$$E_{ads} = U_{tot} - (U_{Ag} + U_{mol})$$

where U_{tot} is the total energy of the metal-molecule assembly, U_{Ag} is the energy of a clean Ag(111) slab, and U_{mol} is the energy of a standalone molecule. In order to avoid trapping in local energy minima on the metal surface, the above procedure was repeated a number of times with different initial conditions and the lowest U_{tot} was used to calculate the adsorption energy E_{ads} . Note that the atoms in the metal slab are fixed and the temperature of the rod assembly is kept constant at 300 K at all times by applying a thermostat. The final set of parameters is presented in Table 3. As a further validation of the new force field for Ag, the adsorption energy of a single thiophene molecule was calculated. The resulting value of 0.56 eV compares favorably with experimental results which are in the range of 0.48-0.64 eV [56].

The importance of image charges in metallic substrates has been demonstrated in several cases [38,39]. To evaluate their effect on the derived parameters, a simpler model was also developed in which the image charges were omitted and the interactions of the metal surface with the organic species occurred only through weak VdW interactions modeled with Lennard-Jones potentials. The same fitting procedure was applied and the resulting parameters are summarized in Table 3. Although the RMS error in the fit is small and comparable to the previous case where rod dipoles were considered, the error in the validation set is larger indicating that the resulting parameters are less transferable to moieties other than those used in the fit. Nevertheless, this simple model is computationally

more efficient since electrostatics with the silver substrate are not involved, and could be used to get initial estimates before using the more accurate model with image charges. In all subsequent simulations only the parameters derived using image charges were employed.

3.2 Adsorption of organic molecules on Ag(111)

3.2.1 Definitions

As a measure of the stability of a layered structure on the Ag(111) surface the normalized formation energy (E_f) was used, defined as

$$E_f = \frac{1}{A} \left[U_{tot} - \left(U_{Ag} + \sum_k U_k \right) \right]$$

where U_{tot} is the total energy of the Ag(111) surface with the organic adsorbates, U_{Ag} is the energy of the pristine surface, U_k is the energy of the k^{th} adsorbed molecule in the gas phase, and A is the area of the substrate. The chosen normalization allows for different sized substrates and in addition enables us to compare the formation energy of different species. In turn, E_f may be decomposed in two contributions as $E_f = E_i + E_m$. The first one is the interfacial energy (E_i) that describes the interactions between the substrate and the adsorbates, and is calculated as

$$E_i = \frac{1}{A} [U_{tot} - (U_{Ag} + U_L)]$$

where U_L is the energy of the adsorbed layer without the substrate. The second contribution is the intermolecular interaction energy (E_m); it stems from the intermolecular interactions among the adsorbed species and is calculated as

$$E_m = \frac{1}{A} \left[U_L - \sum_k U_k \right]$$

To characterize the molecular ordering of the systems the orientation order parameter S was considered. The parameter is calculated using the angle θ between two vectors as

$$S = \left\langle \frac{1}{2} (3 \cos^2 \theta - 1) \right\rangle$$

where brackets denote time and ensemble average. The first vector was defined along a molecular axis while the second either on another molecule or normal to the Ag(111) surface. Depending on how the second vector was defined the order parameter was

calculated as the average between all pairs of molecules (S), or as the average between all molecules (S_z). A schematic of the three vectors used in the calculation of S and S_z are depicted in Fig. 4. The order parameter assumes values in the interval $[-0.5,1]$. A highly ordered configuration is indicated by a value of 1, while for randomly positioned molecules the order parameter is close to 0. Systems with a value of less than 0.3 are considered disordered [55].

3.2.2 Single molecules on Ag(111)

Initially, an individual molecule adsorbed on the Ag(111) surface was considered mimicking a very low surface coverage. A single 3HT8 or PCBM molecule was placed on the surface and the relaxation protocol was applied. The adsorption energy of 3HT8 was found to be 8.5 eV with the molecule lying flat on the substrate at a distance of 3.3 Å. For PCBM the carbon atom closest to the surface was measured at a distance of 3.0 Å. The molecule exhibits a “tail-down” configuration with the methyl-ester group located near the substrate, yielding adsorption energy of 1.7 eV. Single molecule results are summarized in Table 4.

3.2.3 3HT8 layers on Ag(111)

The energetic and structural properties of a full monolayer adsorbed on the Ag(111) surface were calculated using an ideal structure of 3HT8 molecules in an interdigitated layout. Simulations were performed in a range of initial temperatures up to 600 K. Afterwards, the relaxation protocol was employed in order to obtain E_f , E_i and E_m . The results show that the adsorbates relax at a distance of 3.3 Å from the substrate with E_f being 15.9 meV/Å². The major contribution to E_f derives from E_i with 14.7 meV/Å² while intermolecular interactions are negligible. The results for a full 3HT8 monolayer are summarized in Table 5.

In order to investigate the properties of submonolayer covered substrates several samples in the range of 0.05 to 1ML were used. Initial configurations were taken from the vapor growth simulations and were subsequently treated with the relaxation protocol starting from a temperature of 1000 K. As in the case of a full 1ML coverage the adsorbates relax at a distance of 3.3 Å from the substrate. Fig. 5 depicts E_f as a function of surface coverage along with E_i and E_m . It is clear that the linear increase in E_f stems from E_i in the

entire coverage range. Even at dense configurations E_i prevails with the molecules exhibiting only weak intermolecular interactions. The values of E_f , E_i , E_m at maximum coverage are $15.4 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}^2$, $14.4 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}^2$ and $1.0 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}^2$ respectively, which are comparable to those of the ideal structure described previously. This behavior indicates that the substrate is the driving factor for the adsorption of 3HT8.

The effect of thicker coatings on the Ag(111) surface was examined by adding more layers in a lamellar configuration. The cases of 2 and 4ML were considered. The structures were equilibrated at a range of temperatures up to 600 K and the relaxation protocol was employed to obtain the E_f , E_i and E_m . The inset in Fig. 5 shows E_f , E_i and E_m as a function of the number of layers at zero temperature. As expected, the interfacial energy remains almost constant at $16.3 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}^2$ upon addition of more layers, indicating that a single layer is adequate to describe E_i . Past the first layer, intermolecular interactions increase linearly and are the only contribution to the increase in E_f . At the third layer E_m exceeds E_i and intermolecular interactions become the dominant feature of the system.

The thermal stability of 3HT8 coatings was investigated by heating the system and calculating the S order parameter for molecules at the Ag(111)/3HT8 interface. The results are presented in Fig. 6 for 1, 2 and 4 layers of 3HT8. All samples were initially prepared as ideal lamellar structures. It was observed that heating above 400 K induces significant disorder with the monolayer sample being the most affected. For temperatures above 250 K, the 4-layer sample requires an increase of more than 150 K to reach the same extent of disorder as the monolayer sample, demonstrating that a single layer is not suitable to describe the thermally induced disorder. In addition, the 4-layer sample results point to temperatures $\geq 450 \text{ K}$ as most appropriate for inducing intermolecular relaxation and diffusion in a corresponding experimental thermal annealing process. All three samples show no significant difference above 550 K.

3.2.4 PCBM layers on Ag(111)

The properties of a full PCBM monolayer adsorbed on Ag(111) were studied by creating an ideal sample with PCBM molecules regularly placed on the substrate. The relaxation protocol was applied to the structure with several initial temperatures up to 600 K. It was found that the adsorbates relax at a distance of 3.0 \AA from the substrate. The

calculated value for E_f is $30.7 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}^2$ which is significantly higher than the corresponding value for 3HT8. In contrast to the 3HT8 case the major contribution to E_f originates from intermolecular interactions between PCBM species. The calculated value of E_m is $19.3 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}^2$, substantially higher than that of 3HT8. The interaction with the substrate remains important with a value of $11.4 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}^2$ for E_i , although slightly lower than that of 3HT8. These results indicate that PCBM interacts less than 3HT8 with the substrate but can ideally form a much more concrete structure above it. The results for an ideal PCBM monolayer are summarized in Table 5.

PCBM-covered substrates in the submonolayer regime were investigated using several samples in the range of 0.1 to 0.8ML. Starting configurations were taken from the vapor growth simulations and were subsequently treated with the relaxation protocol starting at 1000 K. As in the case of a full 1ML coverage the adsorbates relaxed at a distance of 3.0 \AA from the Ag substrate. Fig. 7 depicts the monolayer formation energy as a function of surface coverage along with the interfacial and intermolecular interaction energies. E_f increases with coverage at a maximum of $23.5 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}^2$, however E_m accounts for a significant percentage of the overall monolayer formation energy as opposed to the 3HT8 case. The two components of E_f are of similar magnitude, with E_i increasing along with E_m and remaining dominant until the highest surface coverage. E_i and E_m contribute to E_f almost equally with $11.9 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}^2$ and $11.5 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}^2$ respectively indicating that intermolecular PCBM interactions play a significant role in the formation of the monolayer. The value of E_i remains comparable to that of the ideal monolayer, however E_m is lower. This is due to the highly dense configuration that was chosen for the ideal structure in which the molecules interact strongly with each other. When compared with 3HT8 the conclusion holds that PCBM interacts less with the substrate forming however a strongly packed monolayer above it.

Although the distance of the fullerene cage from the surface remains the same at all coverages, the orientation of the butyric acid methyl ester group changes, which in turn affects PCBM packing on the substrate. In order to quantify this, the average distance of the PCBM carbonyl oxygen from the substrate was calculated for all coverages, with the results shown in Fig. 8a. There is a clear tendency for PCBM molecules to orient their butyric acid methyl ester group away from the surface. At a low coverage the molecules position the

carbonyl oxygen at a distance of 3.0 Å while as coverage increases the average distance increases to 7.5 Å. To further investigate this behavior, the distribution of PCBM molecules as a function of carbonyl oxygen distance was calculated. Fig. 8b and Fig. 8c depict the results for two representative cases at 0.1ML and 0.8ML respectively. For the 0.1ML case most of the oxygen atoms are placed around 4.3 Å with just a few occurrences around 13.0 Å. For the 0.8ML case there are two regions centered on 4.5 Å and 11.5 Å. It is clear that at low coverage almost all PCBM molecules orient their methyl ester group near the Ag surface while at high coverage, a significant number of molecules orient this group away from the surface.

As in the case of 3HT8, the thermal stability of a single PCBM monolayer was investigated by heating the system and calculating the S , S_z order parameters for molecules at the Ag(111)/PCBM interface (Fig. 9). It was found that although initially all PCBM molecules were placed on the surface on a regular arrangement perfectly aligned to each other, the order is lost ($S < 0.3$) even at temperatures as low as 150K. On the other hand, an average value of 0.46 was observed for S_z at all temperatures suggesting that the molecules remain ordered relative to an axis normal to the surface. Due to the dense packing of the ideal structure the methyl ester groups are hindered from reaching the substrate.

To further examine and validate this behavior for more than 1ML PCBM coatings on Ag(111), a thin isolated slab of PCBM molecules was prepared corresponding approximately to 4ML. The slab was first equilibrated at 900 K, then placed on top of the Ag(111) surface, and the combined system was equilibrated for 59 ns. At various time intervals the first monolayer was examined and the distance of the carbonyl oxygen from the substrate was calculated. The time evolution of the probability distribution is given in Fig. 10a as a series of snapshots at 1, 5, 11 and 59 ns. Remarkably, the peak around 11 Å grows while the simulation progresses, as specified by the arrow. Fig. 10b-d display representative configurations of PCBM molecules taken from the corresponding peaks of the distribution. This system displays a similar behavior as in the 1ML case: a significant number of PCBM molecules orient their methyl ester group away from the surface thus favoring a denser packing on top of the substrate.

4. Conclusions

In this work octi-(3-hexyl-thiophene) (3HT8) was used as model for P3HT and its structural and energetic behavior upon adsorption on the Ag(111) surface was investigated. In addition, 6,6-phenyl C61 butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM) was also considered. Initially, the General Amber Force Field was reparameterized specifically for the main backbone and side chain dihedrals in 3HT8. In addition, two sets of parameters for the interaction of organic molecules with an Ag(111) substrate were created. The first set accounts for both van der Waals and electrostatic interactions between organic molecules and the substrate. The second set corresponds to the introduction of a much faster implementation that only accounts for van der Waals interactions and ignores electrostatic contributions from the substrate.

Subsequently, molecular dynamics simulations using the new force field revealed that PCBM has a higher monolayer formation energy compared to 3HT8. On the contrary, 3HT8 exhibits stronger interactions with the substrate. However, interactions between PCBM molecules are stronger when compared with 3HT8, regardless of the density of the configuration. This leads us to conclude that PCBM can ideally form a more compact structure than 3HT8 on the Ag(111) surface while 3HT8 exhibits stronger adhesion with the substrate. Finally, the dynamic behavior in 3HT8 shows the initiation of intermolecular relaxation and diffusive motion above temperatures of 450 K, while in PCBM the alignment of the methyl ester group leads to a denser packing, on the substrate since the group prefers an orientation away from the surface.

Acknowledgment

This work was supported by the EU FP7 project SMARTONICS (Project No 310229).

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Table 1 Fourier expansion coefficients (Kcal/mol) for dihedrals α and β .

Coefficient	α	β
V_1	-1.125	17.769
V_2	-3.222	10.876
V_3	-0.093	6.609
V_4	0.172	1.243

Table 2 T8 crystal structure.

	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	β (deg)	Density (g/cm ³)
This work	58.8	7.7	6.0	90.3	1.6
Experimental [52]	58.92	7.84	6.00	90.31	1.58

Table 3 Lennard-Jones interaction parameters with the Ag(111) surface.

	With image charges		Without image charges	
	r_0 (Å)	ϵ (kcal/mol)	r_0 (Å)	ϵ (kcal/mol)
Ag-Csp ²	1.935	0.2003	1.922	0.2394
Ag-S	1.747	0.5800	1.710	0.8909
Ag-O(hydroxyl)	1.799	0.3857	1.706	0.8092
Ag-O(carbonyl)	2.228	0.0643	2.063	0.0916
Ag-X	2.322	0.1077	2.165	0.1268
Ag-H	2.216	0.1125	2.691	0.0941
RMS fit error		0.056		0.060
RMS validation error		0.096		0.106

Table 4 Single molecule adsorption energies (E_{ads}) and distances from the surface (d_{ads}).

	E_{ads} (eV)	d_{ads} (Å)
3HT8	8.5	3.3
PCBM	1.7	3.0

Table 5 Full monolayer properties for 3HT8 and PCBM.

	E_f (meV/Å ²)	E_i (meV/Å ²)	E_m (meV/Å ²)	d_{ads} (Å)
3HT8	15.9	14.7	1.2	3.3
PCBM	30.7	11.4	19.3	3.0

Fig. 1. Definition of dihedral angles α , β and atom types for (a) T8 and (b) 3HT8.

Fig. 2. Rotational energy profiles for (a) dihedral angle α , (b) dihedral angle β . The solid pink line corresponds to DFT data, green squares correspond to the atomistic calculations.

Fig. 3. Representation of atom types in the Ag(111) crystal structure. (a) Side view of the surface. (b) Top view of the first layer in the Ag(111) surface. (c) Representation of the rigid rod. Light gray: surface atoms (Ag_{SR}), dark gray: bulk atoms (Ag_{LL}), yellow: virtual atoms (Ag_{SV}). The red rhombus corresponds to the unit cell of the Ag(111) surface. The two red vectors show the positions of Ag_{SV} relative to surface atoms.

Fig. 4. Definition of the vectors used to calculate order parameters (a) across the HT8 backbone, (b) on the PCBM fullerene and normal to the Ag(111) surface.

Fig. 5. 3HT8 interaction energies as a function of coverage. Inset: The energies as a function of the number of 3HT8 layers.

Fig. 6. Order parameter S calculated as a function of temperature for 3HT8 samples with 1, 2 and 3 layers.

Fig. 7. PCBM interaction energies as a function of coverage. Inset: The energies as a function of the number of PCBM layers.

Fig. 8. (a) Average distance of the PCBM carbonyl oxygen from the substrate as a function of coverage. (b) Probability distribution of the PCBM carbonyl oxygen as a function of distance from the substrate when coverage is at 0.1 ML. (c) Same as (b) when coverage is at 0.8 ML.

Fig. 9. Order parameters S , S_z calculated as a function of temperature. S (red line) represents the relative order between molecules. S_z (orange line) represents order of the molecules relative to a director normal to the surface.

Fig. 10. PCBM configurations characterized by the distance of the carbonyl oxygen from the substrate. (a) Time evolution of the probability distribution of carbonyl oxygen as a function of distance from the substrate at 1 ns, 5 ns, 11 ns, 59 ns. Representative PCBM configurations that correspond to (b) first peak - close to the surface, (c) second peak - slightly further from the surface (d) third peak - “tail-up” furthest away from the surface.